

Common Health Problems among Adolescents Attending a Screening Camp in a Medical College of Haryana: A Cross-Sectional StudySunita Vashist¹, Sangeeta Narang², Jeevan Jyoti Meena³, Pradhumn Katara⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine & Health Sciences, SGT University, Gurugram²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine & Health, Sciences, SGT University, Gurugram³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine & Health, Sciences, SGT University, Gurugram⁴Statistician cum Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine & Health Sciences, SGT University, Gurugram

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 15-07-2024 / Accepted: 11-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The objective of this study was to assess the physical health of adolescents including BMI and assess the burden of common health problems among adolescents.**Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in a screening camp held in a medical college in the year 2024 in Haryana after taking ethical approval from the Institutional Ethics committee. A total of 378 adolescents were included in the study. Data was collected using a semi structured, pretested, interview schedule which included Socio-demographic details, clinical history and physical examination of the participants.**Results:** The mean age, weight and height of participants were 15.78 years, 54.66 kg and 163.79 cm, respectively. Majority of them were Hindus (96%), with small percentages being Muslim (2.4%) and others i.e. Sikh, Christians (1.6%). A smaller proportion (10.8%) were overweight, 3.2% of them were obese. 19.8% were thin and 2.6% were severely thin. 16.1% of them were having pallor .7.4 % of the participants had abnormal visual acuity. An extremely small percentage (0.5%) had hearing loss.6.8% of participants were diagnosed as having the nasal septum deviation. A significant proportion had decaying teeth, i.e. 20.9%. There was a significant difference in the presence of pallor, in use of spectacles and presence of tonsillitis.**Conclusion:** This study reveals that a number of common health problems affecting this age group can be diagnosed in a health check-up camp. Early diagnosis and prompt treatment can reduce morbidity and improve the quality of life of adolescents in Haryana.**Keywords:** Adolescent, Body Mass Index, Morbidity, Screening camp.

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Introduction

Adolescents are individuals in the age group of 10-19 years. Adolescence is an important phase of the life between childhood and adulthood as there are rapid changes in the physical and mental health of an individual. They also have to adapt to societal norms and pressures of life. It is imperative to monitor their health status and address their health issues promptly and effectively. In India, where nearly 21% of the population is aged 10-19 years, the health of adolescent school children becomes a matter of paramount concern [1].

Some of the health issues having the potential to significantly impact the overall health and academic performance of adolescents are anaemia, obesity, eye problems, ear, nose, and throat (ENT) problems, and dental problems. Anaemia is a prevalent

nutritional problem in India including Haryana. Consequences of anaemia such as fatigue and impaired cognitive functioning can hinder the scholastic ability of students. Obesity, on the other hand, is a growing global concern, associated with various chronic health issues, including hypertension, diabetes and other heart diseases [2].

Eye problems, including refractive errors and visual impairments, can affect a student's ability to actively learn and participate academically. Similarly, ENT problems can lead to hearing and speech difficulties, potentially affecting communication and learning [3]. Dental problems, such as cavities and gum disease, can also lead to school absenteeism due to dental pain and physical discomfort. Identifying and addressing such health concerns at an early age is

crucial for preventing its long-term health implications. One way to address these issues is through early detection and intervention, which is the primary goal of health screening camps [4]. Understanding the prevalence and patterns of these health issues among adolescent school children is essential for designing effective public health initiatives and school-based health programs. By identifying the most common problems, healthcare providers and educators can work collaboratively to ensure the necessary medical attention and support required by the adolescents, ultimately improving their overall well-being and academic performance [5].

Haryana, a northern state in India, is no exception to this concern, as it contends with unique regional health challenges. The state's rapidly urbanizing population and diversified socio-economic and cultural landscape highlight the need for a comprehensive understanding of the health concerns affecting this vulnerable population.

This study was therefore conducted to assess the prevalence of common health problems, among adolescent school children in a rural area of Haryana.

Aim & Objectives

The objective of this study was to assess the physical health of adolescents which included Body mass index (BMI) and assess the burden of common Ophthalmological, Ear, Nose, Throat and Dental problems.

Materials and Methods

It was a cross-sectional study conducted at a screening camp organized by Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, at SGT Medical College and Research Institute, Haryana. Prior ethical approval was taken from the Institutional Ethics committee. A total of 378 adolescents aged 10-19 years were recruited for the study. All adolescents attending the camp who agreed to participate in the study were included. The investigators explained the nature and purpose of the study to the participants and written informed consent was obtained. Data was collected using a semi structured, pretested, interview schedule. It was divided in 5 sections as follows;

Section 1: Socio-demographic details of the participants such as age, gender, religion, address of school.

Section 2: Clinical History and General physical examination including checking of pallor, Anthropometric measurements such as weight, height and Body Mass Index (BMI). Height was measured by using Measuring tape (non-stretchable) with accuracy to nearest 0.5cm. The participant was asked to stand without footwear or head gear against

a flat surface (wall) with their feet together and with head, shoulders buttocks and heels touching the wall. The participant was asked to look straight ahead and not tilt their head up or down so that an imaginary line drawn from their ear to eye was parallel to the floor. A rigid ruler was placed at right angle with the wall and lowered until it firmly touched the crown of the head. The wall was marked at this point and the distance between point and floor was measured using a measuring tape. Weight of the study participants was done by digital weighing scale measured in kilogram with accuracy to nearest 100gm. The subject was asked to remove his/her footwear and heavy clothing and step onto the scale with one foot on either side of the scale. He/she was asked to stand still, looking straight ahead with arms on the sides till the reading was taken. BMI was calculated using digital calculator by dividing weight in kg by height² in m²

Section 3: Ophthalmological examination included measurement of visual acuity using Snellen's chart [6], checking of colour blindness using Ishihara chart [7], history of use of spectacles and presence of squint. Visual acuity was checked with Snellen's chart. Patient was made to sit at a distance of 6 metre from the Snellen's chart and vision of right eye was checked followed by left eye. Patients with visual acuity 6/6 were included in the normal visual acuity group. Impaired visual acuity was defined with the visual acuity less than 6/12. Number of patients with and without spectacles was also noted. Colour vision was checked with Ishihara chart. Patients unable to see the numbers/patterns in the colour vision chart were included in the abnormal group. Squint was checked with a torchlight. Hirschberg corneal reflex test [8] was done. Patients with abnormal alignment of visual axis with corneal light reflex not falling in the centre of the pupil in either eye were diagnosed to have squint. Number of patients with any other abnormality found on eye examination was also noted.

Section 3: ENT examination including inspection for ear wax, ear discharge, tympanic membrane perforation using otoscope, examination for hearing loss using tuning fork test, looking for deviated nasal septum, mass or polyp in the nose, tonsillitis and pharyngitis. Pre auricular area was inspected for sinus, pit, scar, swelling or any other skin changes and tragal and temporo-mandibular joint tenderness was noted; pinna was assessed for size, shape, position; post auricular area was inspected for any scar, sinus, fistula, swellings or obliteration of post aural groove or any skin changes, and palpated for mastoid tenderness; pinna was then retracted backwards, upwards and laterally to straighten and examine the external auditory canal and any wax or discharge may be cleared to view the tympanic membrane; an otoscope is used to see a magnified view of the tympanic membrane. External nose was

inspected for any deformity, nasal tip was elevated to examine the vestibule; then anterior rhinoscopy was done using a thudicum nasal speculum, and the nasal septum, the turbinates, and floor was examined along with nasal mucosa on both sides.

Oral cavity and oropharynx were inspected using a tongue depressor and a light source, and thoroughly examined from lips, gingiva, teeth, gingival and buccal mucosa, tongue, floor of mouth, hard palate, soft palate, anterior pillars, tonsils and posterior pillar, posterior pharyngeal wall. Larynx was examined using a laryngeal mirror to visualise the base of tongue, vallecula, epiglottis, aryepiglottic folds, false and true vocal cords, and pyriform sinus. Neck was examined for laryngeal crepitus and cervical lymphadenopathy.

Section 4: Dental examination included complete examination of oral cavity for any abnormality such

as dental caries, decaying, missing, filled and broken teeth and history of brushing teeth. The DMFT index⁹ (Decayed, Missing, Filled Teeth index) was used for checking dental caries.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel and then it was analysed using SPSS-PC- 29 trial version. Quantitative data was expressed in mean and standard deviation while qualitative data was expressed in percentage/proportions.

The association between physical health status and gender was tested by chi square test or Fisher's exact test. 'p' value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

Table 1: Socio Demographic details of the Participants (N= 378)

Socio Demographic Details	Gender		
	Female (no %)	Male (no %)	Total (no %)
Type of school			
Govt.	73 (46.7)	124 (55.9)	197 (52.1)
Private	83 (53.3)	98 (44.1)	181 (47.9)
TOTAL	156(100)	222 (100)	378 (100)
Religion			
Hindu	149 (95.5)	214 (96.4)	363 (96)
Muslim	5 (3.2)	4 (1.8)	9 (2.4)
Others	2(1.3)	4 (1.8)	6(1.6)
TOTAL	156(100)	222 (100)	378 (100)
Age			
Mean ± Std. Deviation	15.78 ± 1.34		
Range	12-20		
Weight			
Mean ± Std. Deviation	54.66 ± 12.36		
Range	30-110		
Height			
Mean ± Std. Deviation	163.79 ± 8.66		
Range	142-186		

Table 1 shows socio-demographic details of the study participants. The mean age, weight and height of participants were 15.78 years, 54.66 kg and 163.79 cm, respectively. Majority of them were Hindus (96%), with small percentages being Muslim (2.4%) and others (Sikh, Christians) i.e. 1.6%. There were higher proportion of males (58.7%) as compared to females (41.3%). A slightly higher percentage of the population attended government schools (52.1%) as compared to private schools (47.9%). 53.3% of the females attended private schools as compared to males (44.1%).

Table 2: Common Health Problems of the Participants (N=378)

Variables		Count	Percent
Pallor	Present	61	16.1
	Absent	317	83.9
BMI	Normal (N)	239	63.2
	Overweight (OW)	41	10.8
	Obese (OB)	12	3.2
	Thin (T)	75	19.8
	Severely thin (ST)	10	2.6
Visual acuity	Abnormal	28	7.4

	Normal	350	92.6
Squint	Present	1	0.3
	Absent	377	99.7
Colour vision defect	Present	1	0.3
	Absent	377	99.7
H/o using spectacles	Yes	78	20.6
	No	300	79.4
Ear wax	Present	69	18.3
	Absent	309	81.7
Ear discharge	Present	7	1.9
	Absent	371	98.1
Deviated nasal septum	Present	26	6.9
	Absent	352	93.1
Tonsillitis	Present	63	17
	Absent	315	83.3
Decaying teeth	Present	79	20.9
	Absent	299	79.1

Table 2 shows common health problems of the participants. The majority i.e. 63.2%, of individuals had a normal BMI, indicating a generally healthy weight distribution i.e. 63.2%. A smaller proportion (10.8%) were overweight, 3.2% of them were obese. 19.8% were thin and 2.6% were severely thin. 16.1% of them were having pallor. 7.4% of the participants had abnormal visual acuity. Few individuals i.e. 0.3% had a squint, suggesting that strabismus is not a widespread issue in this sample. Only 0.3% had a colour vision defect. 20.6% of them gave history of

using spectacles, suggesting that visual impairments requiring corrective lenses are not extremely prevalent as compared to 79.4%. 18.3% had ear wax whereas only 1.9% had ear discharge. An extremely small percentage (0.5%) had hearing loss, indicating that it is not a widespread problem. 6.8% of participants were diagnosed as having the nasal septum deviation. The majority (83.3%) do not have tonsillitis. However, a significant proportion has decaying teeth, i.e. 20.9% which indicates dental health issues that might need attention.

Table 3: Association Between Health Problems and Gender (N=378)

Variables		Female	Male	Chi Square Value, Df	P Value
		No. (%)	No. (%)		
Pallor	Present	34 (55.7)	27 (44.3)	6.282, 1	0.01
	Absent	122 (38.5)	195 (61.5)		
BMI	Normal (N)	102 (65.4)	137 (61.7)	3.11, 4	0.53
	Overweight (OW)	13 (8.3)	28 (12.6)		
	Obese (OB)	7 (4.5)	6 (2.7)		
	Thin (T)	31 (19.9)	44 (19.8)		
	Severely thin (ST)	3 (1.9)	7 (3.2)		
Visual acuity	Abnormal	12 (42.9)	16 (57.1)	0.031, 1	0.85
	Normal	144 (44.1)	206 (58.9)		
Squint	Present	1 (100)	0 (0)	1.427, 1	0.23
	Absent	155 (41.1)	222 (58.9)		
Colour vision defect	Present	0 (0)	1 (0.3)	1.327, 1	0.19
	Absent	156 (100)	221 (99.7)		
H/o using spectacles	Yes	46 (59)	32 (41)	12.71, 1	<0.001
	No	110 (36.7)	190 (63.3)		
Ear wax	Present	27 (39.1)	42 (60.9)	0.159, 1	0.69
	Absent	129 (41.7)	180 (5.3)		
Ear discharge	Present	3 (42.9)	4 (57.1)	0.007, 1	0.93
	Absent	153 (41.2)	218 (58.8)		
Deviated nasal septum	Present	8 (30.8)	18 (69.2)	1.270, 1	0.26
	Absent	148 (42)	204 (58)		
Tonsillitis	Present	17 (11.3)	46 (20.2)	5.093, 1	0.02
	Absent	133 (88.7)	182 (79.8)		
Decaying teeth	Present	27 (34.2)	52 (65.8)	2.073, 1	0.15
	Absent	129 (43.1)	170 (56.9)		

Table 3 shows association between health problems of the participants and Gender. There was no significant difference in BMI categories, presence of squint, colour vision defect, presence of ear wax, presence of ear discharge, deviated nasal septum and decaying teeth between both genders indicating fairly similar distribution across variables in both groups. There was a significant difference in the presence of pallor, a higher percentage of females (55.7%) ($p=0.01$) were found to be anaemic, significant difference was also observed in use of spectacles with a higher percentage of females reporting usage i.e. 59% ($p<0.001$). However, tonsillitis was observed more in males i.e. 20.2% ($p=0.02$).

Discussion

The mean age, weight and height of participants are 15.78 years, 54.66 kg and 163.79 cm, respectively. Majority of them are Hindus (96%), with small percentages being Muslim (2.4%) and other i.e. Sikh, Christians (1.6%). There are higher proportion of males (58.7%) as compared to females (41.3%). A slightly higher percentage of the population attended government schools (52.1%) as compared to private schools (47.9%). 53.3% of the females attended private schools as compared to males (44.1%).

In the current study, the proportion of underweight adolescents was found to be 22.4% which is similar to the findings of Salvi SS et al and Darling AM et al. However, the number of overweight and obese adolescents found in our study was less than percentage reported by Salvi et al and more than percentage reported by Darling et al.

In the present study, 55.7% of females were found to have pallor which is similar to NFHS (2019-2021) estimates of anaemia prevalence among Indian adolescent girls (55.8% to 59.1%). However, a high percentage of boys i.e. 58.7% were also found to have pallor in this group as compared to 31% in NFHS-5 [10]. A higher percentage of females (55.7%) ($p=0.01$) were found to be anaemic and Scott S et al also reported higher prevalence of anaemia among adolescents' girls as compared to boys [11].

The prevalence of decaying teeth in the current study was found to be 34.2% in females and 65.8% in males. Dastan M et al [12] and Singh S et al [13] also reported the prevalence of dental caries as 37.5% and 38.5% which is similar to our findings. We observed Deviated nasal septum in 6.9% of the subjects which is lower than the observations of and CB Jan et al [14] and Ashwini et al [15]. The higher prevalence observed by these authors may be due to the fact that they have used radiological aids to diagnose DNS whereas the current study is based on clinical examination alone.

In our study, 20% of the adolescents gave history of using spectacles. These findings are similar to findings of Verma et al [16] who also reported defective visual acuity in 25% participants which is higher than the prevalence of refractive error observed in our study is comparatively higher than the observations of Panda et al [17] which may be due to the fact that visual acuity defect rises with the age and maximum seen in 19-20 years. Colour vision defect found (0.3%) in the current study is lower than that observed by Saha et al [18]. This may be due to fact that the study conducted by Saha R et al was a hospital-based study Mohandas A et al [19] reported prevalence of squint in 0.13% of the adolescents which is similar to our current study.

Shyam G et al [20] reported a higher prevalence of chronic otitis media (7.5%) which is higher than our current study (1.9%) which may be due to the fact that it was a hospital-based study.

Limitations

This was a single camp-based study based on history and physical examination with small sample size, so results of the study cannot be generalized. Detailed examination including laboratory tests and imaging is sometimes needed to confirm the diagnosis and start treatment. Taking this study as reference, research including laboratory investigations and imaging whenever required can be planned.

Conclusion

This study reveals a number of common health problems affecting adolescents in Haryana. Early diagnosis of these preventable problems and prompt intervention can reduce morbidity and improve the health and well-being of this vulnerable population.

There is a need to specifically address the problem of anaemia in girls so that they can develop to their full potential. School based interventions to prevent, diagnose and treat anaemia can save time, manpower as well as money.

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